

Research Aptitudes Among University Teachers and Impacts on Instructional Quality: A Review Paper

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Abstract:

Generating new practices and ideas are the key principles of higher education instructions. For teaching at university level research aptitude, innovative competence and knowledge are becoming increasingly important in today's education. In comparison to other professionals' teachers are required to enhance their aptitude toward research and innovative practices more. Teacher who is engaged in research at his/her professional practice, contributes much to his education career and keep his / her field up to date. A strong research aptitude of university teachers makes a teacher strong,

innovative and productive in his/her teaching profession. The present paper offers reviews of articles and previous studies about aptitude of teachers toward research and the impact on their teaching practices. The review points to the vital importance of research engagement in teaching career. Thus, the investigator argues that there is a greater need of aptitude toward research for teachers who teach at university level.

Keywords: *University Teachers, Research Aptitude, Instructional Quality.*

Introduction

The main mission of 21st century education is to prepare students not only for the present, but also for the ever changing future. This aim comes true with the research-based teaching and innovative performance of teachers at university level. The very first and basic contribution to the fulfilment of today's education will be the teachers' competency and aptitude toward research and investigation for innovative performance in their profession. To understand the aptitude to research, it is defined as a special

characteristic that educators- even more than other professionals, support and develop the teaching professions and put one's one the map in his/ her teaching career, that's why a research work is fundamental part of teaching profession. On the other hand, aptitude is a behavior which every professional needs to acquire in order to have more achievements. Aptitude is the stander upon an individual can show his/her performance. Thus, teachers having more performance and innovation is a sign of their aptitude toward research.

One of the key objective of 21st century teaching and learning process is to raise individual to generate advanced knowledge and reflect their creative, critical, and respectful aptitude toward research. Şahan and Tarhan (2015) argued that scientific aptitudes, thoughts, and actions make people to facilitate actual problem solving in their careers. They generate more comprehensive terms by practicing research techniques and competencies. Ivanenko et, al. (2015) explained research aptitude as the integral quality of teachers. Their study revealed that research aptitude generate ability in teacher find best solution to new problems and transform the reality with questioning, skills, knowledge, and capabilities. For brining such qualities in today's education, many researchers are willing to investigate this dilemma and stimulate teachers to enrich his/ her teaching profession by engaging in research.

Literature Reviews

The study of Ivanenko, et, al. (2015) showed that research aptitude and competence are the essential conditions of improvement in competence and aptitude of teachers' effectiveness. However, the problem is the commitment of modern teachers to research activities. Therefore, the study revealed four basic components for teacher to develop competency and aptitude in research. The four components are methodological reflexive, operational activity, motivational value, and emotional volitional which brings integrity and continuity in competitive teachers.

Sahan & Tarhan (2015) conducted a study on prospective teachers for determining their research competence and research aptitude. The study worked on two dimensions: Descriptive and experimental. The descriptive part has been done to identify their research skills and research aptitude, whereas the experimental part of the study has been done to determine whether the course of scientific methods bring significant difference in their research skills and aptitude or not. Two scales are used to identify the problem: One scale for identifying Research Aptitude and the other scale to identify Scientific Research

Competencies. The study has not found significant difference between the scientific research method course and research competence and aptitude in prospective teachers.

Craig, C. J. (2009) examined from the existing reviews in her article that teachers make up their own minds through appealing in research and change their teaching practices and teaching plans. They add knowledge base teaching to deliver lessons in the class.

Bankauskiene et, al. (2005) studied the variety of the competencies upcoming or a re-qualifying teachers requires. The study revealed that action research helps the teachers to develop their transferable competencies such as self-assessment competence, information and knowledge management competence, research competencies while performing the research. It makes them to negotiate current problems and questions.

Burke et, al. (2005) studied to support research-based practices and introduced evidence based teaching into the curriculum across graduate, undergraduate and post graduate degrees along with doctoral of philosophy programs. The researchers have used evaluation mechanism separately for each academic program, however for doctoral program, they have included comprehensive examination, performance on projects, and program milestone. The study found that the establishment of research-based competencies helped in providing new teaching methods and revision of curricular across each academic program.

Shkedi (1998) studied about research aptitude of teachers. The study attempted to put light on the nature between the literatures of research and teachers. It was a case study in nature. Two parallel channels were kept in consideration: the case study and the case survey. The study illustrated that there is a difference between researchers' world and teachers' world. The study revealed that research literature is not a part of typical teachers' library. The result of the study demonstrated that there exists criticism among teachers. On one hand, teachers accept educational research as positive characteristics of

teaching. On the other hand, the teacher expressed the research unwittingly. This study highlighted that the aptitude toward research of many teachers reflects problem. Usually they complain and make themselves unaware of research when asked for research findings.

Lovat T et, al (1995) cited the work of Rudduck (1985) which argues that there is a need to promote research in teaching education courses. The importance of promoting research in teaching is to increase the level of aptitude, interest and insight of teachers toward research. In the same study the researcher pointed the "action research" as common model and need for teacher to practice. By this way the teacher can study his/her own situation and helps them to find out the teaching process even better.

Zeichner (1993) stated that growing action researches in teaching is the evidence of developing relation of teacher with research and upon many have developed their teaching professions by engaging in action researches. The conclusion of the study shows that teachers are more successful and productive when they are interested and engaged in case studies in their teaching practices.

Houser (1990) reviewed about researchers and teachers and stated that the major problem among them is culture gap that separate the teachers and researchers from one another. They ignore one another also, however they go hand in hands. The researchers interpret, conduct and design studies, while the teachers habitually implement the studies.

Feldman (1987) identified the relationships between teaching and researches. The study explored that "research productivity is positively but very weakly correlated with overall teaching effectiveness". These relationships go in positive direction, but the relation is insignificant. It shows that there is more possibility that research positively effects the subject and teaching.

Hind, Dornbusch & Scott (1974) stated that practically in Stanford faculties give much time to research rather than teaching. (Harry & Goldner,1972; Hoffman,1984; Hoyt&

Spangler,1976; Centra,1983). Their findings well supported Feldman's (1987) also argued that there is no relationship or little relationship between quality of teaching and research productivity.

Conclusion

A strong aptitude toward research makes a teacher strong, innovative and productive in his/her teaching profession. This paper has attempted to provide a review of many researches and articles on university teachers' aptitude toward research. A teacher becomes more strong, advance and innovative when he/she practices research-based and reference-based teaching. It's only possible when a teacher has aptitude toward research and willing to enhance competency in research and investigation.

One of the key objective for today's teachers at university level is to generate advanced knowledge and reflect their creative, critical and respectful aptitude toward research. By reviewing many studies, the investigator found that research aptitude is the integral quality of teachers. This help the teachers to develop their transferable competencies such as self-assessment competence, information and knowledge management competence, research competencies, and bringing innovations in their teaching.

Alongside teaching practices and competencies, many studies stimulated and recommended educators for being part of research engaged team within institution in order to be productive and innovative. On the other hand, the studies showed the effectiveness of research involvement upon teaching and learning process. All in all, the higher education needs professional teachers who are talented, innovative and creative problem solvers.

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